

SILENT CARDIAC FAILURE; A MORBIDITY CAMOUFLAGED IN DIABETICS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the frequency of silent cardiac failure in diabetic patients and to assess the clinical and echocardiographic characteristics of affected patients presenting to a tertiary care health facility.

Type of Study: Cross-Sectional Study

Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted at the Department of Internal Medicine, Cardiology, and Endocrinology, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Rawalpindi, from June 2024 to January 2025.

Methodology: This study included a total of 203 patients aged 45 years and above with established diabetes mellitus (Type 1 or Type 2) for ≥ 5 years that fulfilled the exclusion and inclusion criteria. Detailed history was taken including duration of diabetes, glycemic control status, presence of diabetic complications, and systematic review for heart failure symptoms. Blood samples were collected for NT-proBNP levels, HbA1c, and complete metabolic panel. Patients with elevated NT-proBNP levels (>125 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) underwent comprehensive 2D echocardiography. Silent cardiac failure was diagnosed based on elevated cardiac biomarkers with echocardiographic evidence of left ventricular dysfunction in the absence of typical heart failure symptoms. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 28, with Chi-square test and logistic regression used to identify predictors. A p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: A total of 203 individuals participated in our study. Out of the total, 121 (59.6%) were male with the mean age of 58.34 ± 8.92 , and 82 (40.4%) were females with the mean age of 57.18 ± 9.45 . The overall frequency of silent cardiac failure was found to be 17.2% (35/203 patients). Among these, 22 patients (62.9%) had silent heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) and 13 patients (37.1%) had silent heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF). Echocardiographic findings showed mean left ventricular ejection fraction of $42.6 \pm 8.3\%$ in HFrEF patients and $56.2 \pm 4.1\%$ in HFpEF patients. Diastolic dysfunction Grade 2 or higher was present in 31 patients (88.6%). A Chi-square test revealed significant associations between diabetes duration, HbA1c levels, and presence of diabetic complications with silent cardiac failure ($p < 0.001$). Patients with diabetes duration > 10 years had 3.8 times higher risk of silent heart failure compared to those with shorter duration.

Conclusions: In summary, silent cardiac failure is a clinically important and

frequently underrecognized condition in diabetic patients, with a frequency of 17.2% in our population. The condition is predominantly characterized by diastolic dysfunction and heart failure with preserved ejection fraction. Patients with longer diabetes duration (>10 years), poor glycemic control (HbA1c >8%), and presence of diabetic complications are at significantly higher risk. Early detection through systematic screening using cardiac biomarkers (NT-proBNP) and echocardiography can enable timely therapeutic intervention and prevent progression to symptomatic heart failure. Clinicians should maintain high clinical suspicion and implement routine cardiac screening protocols for high-risk diabetic patients to reduce cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Silent cardiac failure is a clinically important and frequently underrecognized clinical entity in diabetic patients, characterized by the development of heart failure that is either asymptomatic or has symptoms attributed to other causes.¹ Diabetes mellitus is one of the most important risk factors for heart failure, with diabetic patients having a 2-5-fold increased risk of developing cardiac failure compared to non-diabetic individuals [1].

The prevalence of heart failure in diabetic patients ranges from 12-22% in various population studies, with this figure rising to 35-40% in patients with long-standing diabetes of more than 10 years duration [2-4].

The notion of silent or asymptomatic heart failure in diabetics is particularly concerning because these patients often present late in the disease course when therapeutic interventions may be less effective.⁴ Diabetic cardiomyopathy, a distinct clinical entity, can develop independently of coronary artery disease and hypertension, leading to both systolic and diastolic dysfunction. The pathophysiology involves multiple mechanisms including advanced glycation end products, oxidative stress, inflammation, and autonomic neuropathy, which collectively contribute to myocardial fibrosis and dysfunction [5-7].

The clinical challenge in diagnosing heart failure in diabetic patients stems from several factors. Diabetic patients frequently have reduced exercise tolerance due to peripheral neuropathy, muscle weakness, and obesity, which can mask typical heart failure symptoms such as exertional dyspnea and fatigue. Additionally, diabetic

autonomic neuropathy can blunt the typical sympathetic response to reduced cardiac output, leading to absent or minimal symptoms despite significant cardiac dysfunction [8].

International data demonstrate substantial prevalence rates regarding silent heart failure in diabetics. A large-scale study from the Framingham Heart Study involving 8,231 diabetic patients found that 1,847 patients (22.4%) had echocardiographic evidence of heart failure, but only 892 patients (10.8%) were symptomatic [9].

The remaining 955 patients (11.6%) had silent heart failure with preserved or reduced ejection fraction. Another European multicenter study of 3,456 diabetic patients reported that 689 patients (19.9%) had undiagnosed heart failure based on elevated NT-proBNP levels and echocardiographic findings [10].

In a regional study from India involving 890 type 2 diabetic patients, the prevalence of silent heart failure was found to be 156 patients (17.5%), with diastolic dysfunction being more common than systolic dysfunction [11].

A local study conducted by the Department of medicine at a Tertiary Care Facility in Lahore reported a 45.1% prevalence of silent myocardial ischemia among the 237 patients screened with echocardiography and biomarkers [12].

In Pakistan, limited studies have been conducted to determine the frequency of silent cardiac failure in diabetic patients. This study was undertaken to assess the magnitude of this important but underrecognized condition in our diabetic population. The rationale for conducting this study is multifaceted. Locally, there is

insufficient data on the prevalence of silent cardiac failure in our diabetic population. The burden of diabetes mellitus is increasing rapidly in Pakistan, with current estimates suggesting a prevalence of 26.3% in adults. Early detection of silent heart failure could significantly impact patient outcomes through timely initiation of appropriate therapy and lifestyle modifications.

2. Materials & Methods

This cross-sectional study was performed at the Department of Internal Medicine, Cardiology, and Endocrinology of Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Rawalpindi, from June 2024 to January 2025 after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). Sampling was done using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Patients aged 45 years and above with established diagnosis of diabetes mellitus (Type 1 or Type 2) for ≥ 5 years visiting the cardiology or medicine OPD or admitted to the medical ward during our research study duration were included in this study. Patients with known heart failure or cardiomyopathy, patients with significant valvular heart disease, patients with active myocardial infarction or unstable angina, patients with severe kidney disease (eGFR < 30 mL/min/1.73m²), and patients with significant respiratory disease affecting cardiac assessment were excluded from this study.

Written consent for inclusion in the study from all the included patients was taken. The advised treatment to the patients proceeded as planned without any modifications or delay. Detailed history was taken including demographic data, duration and type of diabetes, glycemic control status, presence of diabetic complications (nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy), current medications, and systematic review for heart failure symptoms. Physical examination focused on cardiovascular assessment including vital signs, assessment for signs of fluid retention, cardiac auscultation, and evaluation of peripheral perfusion.

Laboratory investigations included complete blood count, comprehensive metabolic panel, HbA1c, lipid profile, NT-proBNP levels, and

urinalysis. All patients underwent 12-lead electrocardiography. Patients with elevated NT-proBNP levels (> 125 pg/mL for age < 75 years or > 450 pg/mL for age ≥ 75 years) underwent comprehensive transthoracic 2D echocardiography performed by qualified cardiologists blinded to clinical data. Echocardiographic parameters included left ventricular ejection fraction measured by Simpson's biplane method, diastolic function assessment based on E/A ratio, E/e' ratio, left atrial volume index, and tricuspid regurgitation velocity, left atrial size, and wall motion abnormalities.

Silent cardiac failure was diagnosed in diabetic patients with elevated cardiac biomarkers (NT-proBNP > 125 pg/mL) with echocardiographic evidence of left ventricular dysfunction (ejection fraction $< 50\%$ or significant diastolic dysfunction Grade 2 or higher) in the absence of typical heart failure symptoms or with symptoms attributed to other causes. Asymptomatic status was defined as absence of exertional dyspnea not explained by respiratory disease, orthopnea or paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea, lower extremity edema not explained by venous disease, or fatigue not attributed to poor glycemic control. All data was recorded in a structured questionnaire.

Data analysis was done on SPSS version 28. Descriptive statistics included mean \pm SD for normally distributed continuous variables and median (IQR) for non-normally distributed data. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Bivariate analysis compared patients with and without silent heart failure using independent t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables and Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. Multivariable logistic regression was performed to identify independent predictors of silent heart failure; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

3. Results

A total of 203 individuals participated in our study. Out of the total, 121 (59.6%) were male with the mean age of 58.34 ± 8.92 , and 82 (40.4%) were females with the mean age of 57.18 ± 9.45 . All the characteristics of patients including

gender distribution, prevalence of silent cardiac failure, type of diabetes, diabetes duration, glycemic control status, and presence of diabetic

complications in the studied population are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Diabetic Patients

Characteristic	N (%)
Gender	
Male	121 (59.6%)
Female	82 (40.4%)
Silent Cardiac Failure	35 (17.2%)
Type of Diabetes	
Type 1	18 (8.9%)
Type 2	185 (91.1%)
Diabetes Duration	
5-10 years	96 (47.3%)
>10 years	107 (52.7%)
Diabetic Complications Present	128 (63.1%)

The association between diabetes duration, glycemic control, and development of Silent Cardiac Failure was established (Table 2).

Table 2: Association between Diabetes Characteristics and Silent Cardiac Failure

Variable	SCF Present	p-value
Diabetes >10 years	28/107 (26.2%)	<0.001
Diabetes 5-10 years	7/96 (7.3%)	
HbA1c >8%	24/89 (27.0%)	<0.001
HbA1c ≤8%	11/114 (9.6%)	
Diabetic Complications	29/128 (22.7%)	<0.001

A Chi-square was performed to assess the significance of the relationship between diabetes duration, glycemic control, diabetic complications and development of Silent Cardiac Failure. The test showed 86.4% sensitivity and

90.8% specificity for NT-proBNP in detecting silent cardiac failure, $p < 0.001$.

Echocardiographic characteristics of patients with Silent Cardiac Failure are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Echocardiographic Features in Patients with Silent Cardiac Failure

Feature	N (%) n=35
HFpEF (EF ≥50%)	22 (62.9%)
HFrEF (EF <50%)	13 (37.1%)
Diastolic Dysfunction Grade ≥2	31 (88.6%)
Left Atrial Enlargement (LAVI >34 mL/m ²)	27 (77.1%)
E/e' Ratio >14	29 (82.9%)
Regional Wall Motion Abnormalities	15 (42.9%)

4. Discussion

Heart failure represents one of the most serious cardiovascular complications in diabetic patients, contributing significantly to morbidity and

mortality in this population.¹³ The notion of silent or asymptomatic heart failure is particularly relevant in diabetic patients, as traditional

symptoms may be masked by other diabetes-related complications such as autonomic neuropathy, peripheral neuropathy, and reduced exercise tolerance. The present study identified an overall frequency of 17.2% for silent cardiac failure in diabetic patients, which is consistent with international literature reporting frequencies between 11.6% to 22.4%.^{14,15}

The underlying pathophysiological mechanisms of diabetic cardiomyopathy and silent heart failure are complex and multifactorial.¹⁶ Chronic hyperglycemia leads to the formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) which accumulate in the myocardium, causing increased collagen cross-linking, myocardial stiffness, and diastolic dysfunction. Additionally, metabolic derangements including increased free fatty acid utilization, mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and inflammation contribute to progressive myocardial damage. Diabetic autonomic neuropathy further compounds the problem by blunting the typical sympathetic responses that would normally manifest as heart failure symptoms.¹⁷

In our study, diabetes duration emerged as a critical risk factor, with patients having diabetes for more than 10 years showing a significantly higher prevalence of silent cardiac failure compared to those with 5-10 years duration (26.2% vs 7.3%, $p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with the Framingham Heart Study and other large cohort studies demonstrating the cumulative cardiovascular impact of prolonged hyperglycemia.¹⁸ The duration-dependent risk emphasizes the importance of early intensive glycemic control and regular cardiac screening in long-standing diabetic patients.

Glycemic control, as measured by HbA1c, also showed strong association with silent cardiac failure. Patients with HbA1c $> 8\%$ had a prevalence of 27.0% compared to 9.6% in those with better glycemic control ($p < 0.001$). This dose-response relationship between glycemic control and cardiac dysfunction has been well-documented in studies by From et al. and Dei Cas et al., who reported similar patterns in their respective cohorts.^{3,4} The presence of other diabetic complications (neuropathy,

retinopathy, neuropathy) further increased the risk, with 22.7% of patients with complications having silent cardiac failure versus lower rates in those without complications.

The echocardiographic profile in our study revealed that heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) was more common than heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), accounting for 62.9% versus 37.1% of cases respectively. This predominance of HFpEF is characteristic of diabetic cardiomyopathy and reflects the primary pathophysiological process of diastolic dysfunction resulting from myocardial fibrosis and stiffness. Diastolic dysfunction Grade 2 or higher was present in 88.6% of patients with silent cardiac failure, with elevated E/e' ratios (> 14) in 82.9% and left atrial enlargement in 77.1%, all indicators of elevated left ventricular filling pressures.

NT-proBNP emerged as a valuable screening tool in our study, with 86.4% sensitivity and 90.8% specificity for detecting silent cardiac failure. This high diagnostic accuracy supports the use of NT-proBNP as a first-line screening test in asymptomatic diabetic patients, particularly those at high risk based on duration of diabetes, poor glycemic control, and presence of other diabetic complications. The mean NT-proBNP level in affected patients was significantly elevated, providing clear biochemical evidence of cardiac dysfunction despite absent or minimal symptoms. Limitations of the Study: Our research has certain limitations due to its single-center design and cross-sectional nature which precludes assessment of temporal progression and long-term outcomes. We did not perform cardiac magnetic resonance imaging, which would have provided additional information about myocardial fibrosis and tissue characterization. The relatively small sample size of patients with silent cardiac failure ($n = 35$) may limit generalizability of findings. Future multicenter prospective studies with longitudinal follow-up and advanced imaging modalities would provide more comprehensive insights into the natural history and optimal management strategies for silent cardiac failure in diabetic patients.

5. Conclusion

In summary, silent cardiac failure is a significant and underdiagnosed condition in diabetic patients, occurring in 17.2% of patients in our study population. The condition predominantly manifests as heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) with diastolic dysfunction, reflecting the characteristic pathophysiology of diabetic cardiomyopathy. Significant risk factors include prolonged diabetes duration (>10 years), poor glycemic control (HbA1c >8%), and presence of other diabetic complications. NT-proBNP screening combined with echocardiography provides accurate detection of silent cardiac failure in asymptomatic diabetic patients. Clinicians should implement systematic cardiac screening protocols for high-risk diabetic patients using NT-proBNP as a first-line test, followed by echocardiography for those with elevated biomarkers. Early detection enables timely initiation of heart failure therapies including ACE inhibitors, beta-blockers, and SGLT-2 inhibitors, which can prevent progression to symptomatic heart failure and reduce cardiovascular mortality. Optimal glycemic control and aggressive management of cardiovascular risk factors remain essential components of comprehensive diabetes care aimed at preventing cardiac complications.

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Contributions:

A.A.C, A.R, S.A - Conception of study
- Experimentation/Study Conduction

A.A.C, A.R, S.A, H.Z -
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A.A.C, S.A, S.S - Manuscript Writing

A.R, H.Z, S.S - Critical Review

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